

REQUIREMENTS:

The virtual machine image (Vneo4j.ova) has been created using Oracle VM VirtualBox 7.0 and runs on the Ubuntu 18.04.6-desktop-amd64 operating system. All the necessary environments have been configured, including the matching version of variability-aware Rex (executable included in the virtual machine) and Neo4j Community Edition 4.3.11.

We have ensured consistency by selecting the same versions of all environments and tools mentioned in our paper. The virtual machine image size is approximately 8GB and requires around 20GB of space when fully loaded. The virtual machine's capacity is set to 50GB, which should be sufficient for most experiments.

Importing the virtual machine image into Oracle VM VirtualBox and following the instructions provided in README.pdf should enable users to run our experiments. The username and password for the virtual machine are both vneo4j.